
Deliverable D-JIP2-D1.7: Closing symposium Workpackage 1

Responsible Partner: RIVM

Contributing partners: All partners

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Deliverable	D-JIP End symposium
WP and Task	JIP-WP1 Task End symposium for all partners and all interested parties to to share results and products of COHESIVE
Leader	Kitty Maassen
Other contributors	All COHESIVE partners
Due month of the deliverable	48
Actual submission month	47
Type <i>R: Document, report</i> <i>DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.</i> <i>OTHER</i>	OTHER: Meeting on-site & on-line
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public</i> <i>CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PUBLIC

Summary COHESIVE Closing Symposium November 8, 9 and 10 2021. Virtual and live in Bilthoven

Participants

Adriano Di Pasquale (IZSAM), Agustin Conesa (EFSA), Aivars Bērziņš (EFSA) Alessandro De Luca (DIAG), Andrea Bucc, Andrea Osborn (Canada), Aniek Messink (RIVM), Annemarie Käsbohrer (VETMEDUNI), Antonio Rinaldi (IZS), Arjan Stroo (NVWA), Aura Andreassen (DKSund), Carlus Deneke (BfR), Caroline Eves (DKSund), Cecilia Mia Wolff (NVI), Cesare Cammà (IZS-AM), Charlotte Cook (APHA), Clemence Foltz (EFSA), Eduardo de Freitas Costa (WUR), Elaine Campling (School of Vet Med.), Elina Lahti (SVA), Mahbod Entezami (School of Vet Med.), Erika Scaltriti (IZLER), Estelle Ågren (SVA), Francesca Cito (EFSA), Frits Vlaanderen (RIVM), George Sips (RIVM), Geraldine Boseret (Sciensano), Guido Benedetti (DKSund), Gunel Ismayilova (FAO), Hein Imberechts (Sciensano), Helena Juricova (VRI), Helle Daugaard Larsen (DKSund), Henriette de Valk (SPF), Holger Brendebach (BfR), Iliaria Menozzi (IZLER), Ingrid Friesema (RIVM), Jakub Fusiak (BfR), Jelani Febis (RIVM), Johanna Dups-Bergmann (FLI), Johanne Ellis -Iversen (FVST, DK), Joke van der Giessen (RIVM), Joukje Siebenga (WUR), Karin Artursson (SVA), Karin Nyberg (SLV), Kaylee Errecaborde (WHO), Kitty Maassen (RIVM), Krishna Adhikari, Laura Gonzalez Villeta (School of Vet Med.), Linda Vrbova (PHAC/ASPC), Lindqvist Roland (SLV), Lisa Kohnle (City University of Hong Kong), Luca Bolzoni (IZSLER), Ludovico Sepe (BfR), Malin Jonsson (NVI), Mathilde Uiterwijk (NVWA/RIVM), Marcel Spierenburg (NVWA), Maria Nöremark (SVA), Marie Nykvist (SVA), Marie-Claire Pay, Mariia Galaburda (Univ Ukraine), Marion Gottschald (EFSA), Mauro De Rosa, (NVWA), Mia Holmberg (SVA), Michele Luca D'errico (ISS), Mireille D'Astous, Mirko Rossi (EFSA), Monica Ferrilli, Naomi Zouteriks (RIVM), Nathalie JOURDAN-DA SILVA (SPF), Nattakarn Awaiwanont (BfR), Nicolas Radomski (GENPAT-IZSAM), Olaug Taran Skjerdal (NVI), Ömer Keskin (RIVM), Pieter-Jan Ceyskens (Sciensano), Pikka Jokelainen (DKSund), Pilar Garcia Vello (EFSA), Renaud Lailler (ANSES), Ricardo Pedro Moreira Dias, Rickard Knutsson (SVA), Rob Dewar (APHA), Robert Opitz (BfR), Robert Puschmann (BfR), Robin Simons (APHA), Sandra Cavaco Gonçalves (INIAV), Sean Shadomy (FAO), Sharon Calvin (Canada), Simon Rüegg (Univ Zurich), Simon Tausch (BfR), Simone Severs-Mommers (RIVM), Sofie de broe (Sciensano), Solveig Jore (FHI), Stephen Wyllie, Stine Kjær Lefèvre (SSI), Tamas Bakonyi (ECDC), Tineke Kramer (RIVM), Valentina Rizzi (EFSA), Violetta Costanzo (EPHA), Vítor Borges (INSA), Wim van der Poel (WBVR), Zuzana Nordeng (DKSund), Галабурда Марія Алімівна

In total over 100 people attended this symposium. In addition to COHESIVE and OHEJP members, interest was shown from our stakeholders EFSA, ECDC, FAO and WHO and from outside the OHEJP consortium even outside Europe.

Workpackages of COHESIVE

In this closing symposium all tasks were discussed. Below the tasks and task leaders

WPs, tasks & leaders:
WP1 Coordination, communication and sustainability (Kitty Maassen, RIVM)
1.1 Coordination (Kitty Maassen, RIVM)
1.2 Communication/Dissemination (Kitty Maassen, RIVM)
WP2 Integrated risk-analysis at the national level (Kitty Maassen, RIVM)
2.1 Implementation guidelines for One Health Risk Analysis Structures (Kitty Maassen, RIVM)
2.2 Decision tool to support One Health Risk Assessment (Rob Dewar, APHA)
2.3 Pilots of implementation guidelines for One Health Risk Analysis Structures (Kitty Maassen, RIVM)
WP3 Towards an EU zoonoses structure (Elina Lahti, SVA)
3.1 Exchange of early signals of zoonotic events within and between countries in Europe – barriers and facilitating factors (Maria Nöremark, SVA)
3.2 Select tools for Horizon scanning and signal detection (Rickard Knutsson, SVA)
3.3 Retrospective systems analysis of detection of outbreaks (Rob Dewar, APHA)
3.4 Pilots One Health early warning system (Elina Lahti, SVA)
3.5 Development of tool for systematic cost-benefit analysis (Robin Simons, APHA)
WP4 Data platform to facilitate risk-analysis and outbreak control (Adriano Di Pasquale, IZS-AM)
4.1 Molecular typing data and metadata – database implementation (Adriano Di Pasquale, IZS-AM)
4.2 Development of a platform-independent tracing framework (Marion Gottschald, BfR)
4.3 Development of a platform-independent risk modeling framework (Thomas Selhorst, BfR)
4.4 Dissemination (Marion Gottschald)

Program

Day 1. November 8, 2021

Sharing signals and information

09.00-09.30 Coffee and registration

09.30-09.45 Welcome

09.45-10.30 Introduction to COHESIVE

10.30-11.00 COHESIVE Information system WP4 (Adriano Di Pasquale, IZS-AM)

The aim was to develop a prototype information system at the national level allowing public health and veterinarian organisations to test interoperability of their WGS data archives. Three feasibility studies have been carried out on Italy, The Netherlands and Norway.

11.00-11.30 Break

11.30-12.30 COHESIVE Information system WP4 (demonstration, also online)

Demonstration of the Italian version of the COHESIVE prototype information system.

12.30-13.30 Lunch

13.30-14.00 Low threshold sharing of signals cross countries WP3 (Elina Lahti, SVA)

Signals often are shared between countries within their own sector, but not across sectors. We are setting up meetings to accommodate low threshold sharing of information cross countries. A spin off was a workshop on B. canis.

14.00-14.30 Drivers of One Health by horizon scanning WP3 (Rickard Knutsson, SVA)

Horizon scanning is a foresight methodology that can be used for identifying threats, challenges and drivers within One Health. A literature review of the available tools was conducted as well as two exercises to assess future challenges.

14.30-14.45 Break

14.45-15.30 Guidelines OH Risk analysis systems WP2 (Kitty Maassen, RIVM)

The goal was to develop guidelines to support countries in setting up or strengthen the collaboration in the area of risk analysis (signalling, risk assessment and risk management) of zoonoses. The why, the how and the what of this development will be shared.

15.30-17.00 Guidelines OH Risk analysis systems WP2 (workshop, also online)

During this workshop, we will focus on the implementation process, which is defined in 5 steps. A computer is needed.

~19.00 Dinner together (Bilthoven)

Day 2. November 9, 2021

Response and barriers in One Health collaboration

09.00-09.45 Formal and informal signalling pathways WP3 (Maria Nöremark, SVA)

Sharing early signals of a potential outbreak can contribute to control of the outbreak and minimize the consequences, and sharing information between sectors (animal health, food safety, public health) is often necessary. In this study, factors facilitating signal sharing as well as barriers for sharing information were identified, both on national and international level. Data was collected through in-depth interviews with experts working with animal health, food safety or public health in six different countries.

09.45-09.55 Break

09.55-10.45 Barriers in One Health collaboration WP2 (workshop, also online)

In the process of discussing on implementing a One Health risk analysis system (OHRAS), we also discussed what hampers One Health collaboration. Out of the many identified barriers 4 were selected to be addressed in the guidelines for setting up a OHRAS, gaining political will, trust, sharing information and communication. We like to reflect with you on those and other barriers during the workshop.

10.45-11.15 Break

11.15-12.00 Experiences of systems thinking workshops WP2 (Cecilia Wolff)

Step 3 of the implementation process of setting up a risk analysis system for zoonoses, is mapping the current system. Experiences of a live workshop in Norway and a virtual workshop will be shared.

12.00-13.00 Lunch

13.00-14.00 Decision support tool to assist risk assessors WP2 (workshop, also online)

Risk analysis is varied, and it is often challenging to settle on an approach that suits the constraints of your situation. Here, we present a decision-support tool to help with this. It is built to guide users towards their most appropriate risk assessment method using a decision-tree of questions; we hope to demonstrate this interactively.

Aim of the Decision support tool:

- *Assembly of risk assessment resources*
- *Isolate different approaches*
- *Discern the key decision-making themes*
- *Use these themes to develop a decision tree*

The decision tree is published as an online tool: <https://cohesive.onehealthejp.eu/>

14.00-14.10 Break

14.10-15.30 FoodChain-Lab Web: An integrative modular software to visualise and analyse complex global food supply chain networks during foodborne incidents WP4 (workshop, also online)

The workshop contains a lecture and an interactive live-demo of FCL Web. For this, participants need to bring their laptops with Firefox or Chrome as browser. There will also be a short presentation on the NOVA likelihood tool which is currently being integrated into FCL Web.

15.30-16.15 Steering group meeting (WP and task leaders COHESIVE only)

16.30- Social program and dinner (around Utrecht)

Day 3. November 10, 2021

Looking into the future

09.00-09.30 Retrospective analysis of Q fever by systems mapping WP3 (Rob Dewar, APHA)

Understanding a public information system is particularly challenging when a disease is not notifiable or reportable. Here we outline two systems mapping approaches for visualizing public information systems and surveillance/reporting pathways when a disease is not reportable or notifiable. We present some findings from this exercise.

09.30-10.00 Systematic cost-benefit analysis WP3 (Rob Dewar, APHA)

Economic analyses for foodborne diseases are varied. Their methodologies, terminologies, and outputs are sometimes inconsistent or confusing to the people analyzing or conducting them. A systematic review of these economic analyses attempts to deconvolute the subject, showcasing and explaining the similarities and differences between the range of methods applied.

10.00-10.10 Break

10.10-11.30 Quantitative stochastic risk assessment with the “shinyRisk” app (Demonstration)(Robert Opitz, BfR)

The app “shinyRisk” is intended to simplify the process of creating, documenting, evaluating, and analysing a model for stochastic quantitative risk assessment. It is the goal to make this process more clearer and more transparent, but it also tries to standardise this process. Great importance is attached to simple usability and complete transparent description of the model. The aim is to make the assessment model and its results available to all stakeholders in the assessment process in a well-documented and easily readable form. The app can also automatically generate a report of the model. In the first part, it is intended to demonstrate the app. But, we also want to show future developments.

11.30-12.30 Quantitative stochastic risk assessment with the “shinyRisk” app (hands on workshop in Bilthoven) (Robert Opitz, BfR)

In this part we will deepen the introduction of shinyRisk by going through the risk assessment process with concrete examples. We invite everyone to bring their own models that we could use as a case study for a stochastic quantitative risk assessment process.

12.30-13.30 Lunch

13.30-14.30 What is next?

14.30-15.00 Wrap-up, feedback and closure open part of the symposium

15.00-15.30 Break

15.30-16.15 Discussion general items COHESIVE (members COHESIVE only)

Reflection

As can be seen from the program all tasks were presented and discussed. All tools were demonstrated or worked with in workshops. Almost everything could be followed online. Specifically in the workshops there were enthusiastic and fruitful discussions. Still (practical) feedback was gathered for further improvement of the tools. And very promising contacts were made to help implement (and improve) tools, for instance the CIS and Shiny Risk. An important reflection is that there is a clear need for promoting and implementing all developed tools as well the acquired knowledge and insights after COHESIVE ends.

Presentations

The presentations can be found at the OHEJP website [COHESIVEmembers - One Health EJP](#) in the folder of the end symposium